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6G Goal-**O**riented **A**I-enabled **L**earning and **S**emantic Communication Networks
(6G-GOALS)

Deliverable D2.1

Reference system, scenarios, use-case analysis, and requirements: first results

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Abstract

This is the first deliverable of the 6G-GOALS project, which aims to present the reference system, scenarios, use-cases, and requirements. Firstly, we briefly introduce the vision of the 6G-GOALS project toward the next-generation semantic and goal-oriented communication paradigm. We then identify and analyse the important use-cases that can benefit from this new communication paradigm, taxonomising them into: multimedia-centric use-cases, task-oriented use-cases, network management use-cases, and Internet of Things (IoT) use-cases. A total of thirteen use-cases have been described. For each use-case, we provide a detailed description, identify the system requirements, explain how goal-oriented semantic communication is beneficial, and outline the relevant key performance indicators (KPIs) and metrics. Besides, we propose a taxonomy of system design requirements. These requirements are examined from different perspectives, including architecture, functionality, management and orchestration, integration and backward compatibility, use-cases, and performance. To realise semantic awareness, we emphasise the design considerations for each requirement category, particularly from the perspectives of radio access network (RAN) and core network.

Keywords

AI-native, use-cases, multimedia, task-oriented, semantic, network management, IoT, system requirements, architecture, orchestration, performance, goal-oriented.

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5th Generation
6G	6th Generation
AF	Application Function
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMF	Access and mobility Management Function
AV	Autonomous Vehicle
BCI	Brain-Computer Interfaces
BS	Base Station
CU	Centralised Unit
DT	Digital Twin
DU	Distributed Unit
EEG	Electroencephalography
EMF	Electromagnetic Field
EMS	Element Management System
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
IoT	Internet-of-Things
ITR	Information Transfer Rate
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLM	Large Language Model
LPWA	Low-Power Wide-Area
M&O	Management and orchestration
MAC	Medium Access Control
MCL	Maximum Coupling Loss
MEG	Magnetoencephalography
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	ML Operations
mMTC	massive Machine-Type Communication
MR	Mixed Reality
NAS	Non-Access Stratum
NB-IoT	Narrowband-IoT
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
O-RAN	Open RAN
OAM	Operation Administration and Maintenance
PDU	Protocol Data Unit
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RU	Radio Unit
SemCom	Semantic Communication
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMF	Session Management Function
SSRF	Semantic State Repository Function
TWI	Time Window of Integration

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UE	User Equipment
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2P	Vehicle-to-Pedestrian
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives of this deliverable

Rooted in the seminal work of Shannon and Weaver and emerging as a pivotal research theme in wireless communications, semantic and goal-oriented communication represents a promising paradigm for the future. The 6G-GOALS project is dedicated to delving into the foundational aspects and feasibility of integrating semantic and goal-oriented communication into the 6th Generation (6G) network. This involves establishing precise mathematical definitions, seamlessly integrating these concepts into the network architecture, and demonstrating their practical applications through real-world scenarios.

At the core of this project lies the task of defining the reference system, scenarios, use-cases, and requirements necessary for realising the envisioned paradigm shift. This deliverable describes the reference system and scenarios wherein semantic and goal-oriented communication can transcend the limitations of traditional communication protocols. Additionally, it investigates potential applications leveraging Semantic Communication (SemCom) in different domains, offering a comprehensive analysis of their business, technical, and operational requirements. As a key input for other Work Packages (WPs), this deliverable serves to guide and scope out the technical activities, ultimately contributing towards the success of the project.

1.2 The 6G-GOALS's approach and vision

In the existing literature, a universally accepted definition of SemCom has not yet been established. We adopt a broad interpretation of the term "semantic" to encompass any structural (topological), statistical, or causal relationships within the data being processed and communicated, evaluated in the context of the desired reconstruction metric or the intended actions at the receiver's end. Consequently, 6G technologies, algorithms, and protocols must be designed to extract, process, and deliver the appropriate information at the right time to achieve the desired effectiveness. For instance, consider the transmission of an image over a wireless link. The specific information that needs to be extracted and conveyed varies based on the receiver's objective. If the goal is to provide the highest Quality of Experience (QoE) to a human receiver, all perceptually relevant information must be transmitted. On the other hand, if the image is being sent to an Artificial Intelligence (AI) classifier, it may be sufficient to convey only the features relevant to classification. Similarly, for image retrieval purposes, distinguishing features that facilitate efficient database searching are the primary concern. Therefore, the requirements for information extraction and transmission differ significantly depending on the end-use case.

The 6G-GOALS project aims to lay the theoretical, algorithmic, and operational foundations of a novel communication and networking paradigm that moves beyond the established sense-compute-connect-control models toward semantic and goal-oriented communications. This new paradigm will be based on AI-enabled architectures, protocols, and services. Unlike the current content-agnostic approach, where data are transmitted without understanding its informativeness for the communication's end-goal, 6G-GOALS emphasises pragmatic and judicious generation, manipulation, storage, transmission, and reconstruction of information. By leveraging the semantic relevance of contextual data and incorporating the latest advances in AI and Machine Learning (ML) technologies, 6G-GOALS will integrate this intelligence into network design. This approach challenges the existing paradigm by ensuring that only the most relevant and important information is transmitted, thereby optimizing the communication process in line with the specific objectives and context of the receiver. The project introduces several key innovations that redefine how we approach wireless communication and networking. First, it shifts the focus from traditional radio link Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as spectral efficiency and throughput to new measures that assess goal precision, learning capability, real-

time operation, privacy, and data value, considering their trade-offs with energy efficiency. This redefinition of KPIs is fundamental to adapting the network to more context-aware and purpose-driven metrics (details of new KPIs definition can be found in [D2.2]). Second, 6G-GOALS involves designing a new class of AI-based wireless communication technologies that incorporate both the semantic and pragmatic aspects of data. These technologies will enable more intelligent and context-aware data processing and transmission, enhancing overall communication efficiency and effectiveness. Third, the development of an intelligent Radio Access Network (RAN) is central to the project. This RAN will control adaptive L1/L2 functions with increasing complexity at the Radio Unit (RU) end, facilitating the realization of the new semantic-oriented communication paradigm. This innovation allows for a more dynamic and responsive network infrastructure that can adapt to varying communication needs. Fourth, the project focuses on creating novel AI/ML technologies to support adaptive bandwidth demands and versatile spectrum usage. This innovation enables the coexistence between users of conventional systems and those of SemCom systems, ensuring a more harmonious and efficient use of available resources. Fifth, 6G-GOALS develops mixed data-driven and model-based AI technologies to ensure that 6G systems retain reliability, energy efficiency, and low Electromagnetic Field (EMF) characteristics. This blend of approaches leverages the strengths of both data-driven insights and established model-based techniques to optimise network performance. Finally, the project will implement a proof of concept and a field trial where a network of collaborative robots shares essential semantic information to make collaborative decisions towards achieving a final goal. This real-world application demonstrates the practical viability and benefits of the proposed SemCom framework.

The innovations introduced by 6G-GOALS can be grouped into three main research and innovation areas. First, AI-empowered semantic data representation, sensing, compression, and communication will be developed to enhance how data is handled and transmitted. Second, advancements in time-sensitive communication over wireless links will ensure that critical data is transmitted within the required timing constraints. Third, the project emphasises sustainability by developing technologies that enable new wireless services with higher efficiency, contributing to a more sustainable communication infrastructure. Central to the advancement of this project and the achievement of its vision is the task of defining the reference system, scenarios, use-cases, and requirements essential for achieving this paradigm shift, which is the main purpose of this deliverable. To be more specific, we will identify and define scenarios and use-cases where ML-aided semantic goal-oriented communication and networking can surpass conventional protocols by integrating sensing, computation, learning, and intelligent decision-making. The objective is to provide insights and recommendations for designing and deploying heterogeneous applications and services that leverage semantic-empowered communication to enhance user experience, boost network efficiency, and improve resource utilization and decision-making processes [SDS+24].

1.3 Structure of this deliverable

The remaining sections of this deliverable are organised as follows. Section 2 provides a brief overview of the methodology used to identify and categorise the use-cases and system requirements. Section 3 presents the taxonomy of the identified use-cases, elaborating on each of them in detail. This section includes descriptions of all 13 use-cases, divided into multimedia-centric, task-oriented, network management, and Internet-of-Things (IoT) categories. For each use-case, we explore its specific characteristics, potential benefits from the new communication paradigm, and the associated system requirements. Additionally, we discuss the practical implications and real-world applications of each use-case. Section 4 delves into the system requirement taxonomy, examining the various requirements necessary to support the identified use-cases. This section is structured to cover multiple perspectives, including architectural, functional, management and orchestration, integration and compatibility, and performance. We

emphasise the importance of these requirements in achieving semantic awareness, highlighting the critical design considerations for RAN and core network design. The section presents a synthesis of how these requirements interrelate to support the overarching goals of the 6G-GOALS project. Section 5 concludes this deliverable.

2 Methodology

This deliverable aims to establish a shared foundation and provide comprehensive insights and recommendations to guide the research efforts of other WPs within the 6G-GOALS project. This foundational work is critical to ensure alignment and coherence across various technical aspects of the project, facilitating seamless integration and innovation.

Identification of scenarios and use-cases

A key component of this deliverable is the identification and thorough analysis of scenarios and use-cases that can significantly benefit from AI-based SemCom. The primary goals in this context are to enhance communication quality, reduce communication overhead, and improve overall network operational efficiency. Particular considerations are given to the overlapping use-cases for semantic and goal-oriented communications, vertical application, AI-native networks, generative AI, and 6G.

Reference system architecture and design requirements

The reference system architecture builds upon state-of-the-art 5th Generation (5G) and Open RAN (O-RAN) systems, with a focus on native AI enhancements oriented towards 6G. The system design requirements are examined comprehensively from multiple perspectives to fully unleash the potential of semantic communication at scale. Special emphasis is placed on the design considerations for the RAN and core network components. By empowering the semantic and goal-aware Open RAN, we aim to enhance the network's ability to process and interpret semantic information, leading to more intelligent and efficient communication systems.

This methodology sets the stage for the 6G-GOALS project by identifying key scenarios and use-cases and establishing comprehensive system design requirements for forward-looking reference architecture. These efforts are directed towards harnessing the full power of AI-based semantic communication, paving the way for the next generation of intelligent, goal-oriented communication networks.

3 Taxonomy of use-cases

In this section, we develop a taxonomy of use-cases through analysis of their objectives, features, and stakeholders. This ensures a comprehensive understanding of each use-case and facilitates a unified structured classification system.

Within each category of use-cases, we provide detailed definitions for every item, enumerate representative examples, and depict the specific objectives associated with each use-case. Furthermore, we delve into the synergies between these use-cases and goal-oriented SemCom, elucidating how this innovative communication paradigm enhances each use-case and identifying potential requirements for the system architecture.

Additionally, we identify KPIs and metrics that can be leveraged for the validation and assessment of each use-case. The formal definition of the KPIs and metrics used by the project and the expected value of range attained by 6G-GOALS are presented in [D2.2].

This comprehensive approach ensures that our taxonomy not only categorises use-cases effectively but also provides actionable insights for their implementation and evaluation.

3.1 Multimedia-centric use-cases

As we delve deeper into the transformative potential of 6G and SemCom for multimedia-centric applications, it becomes evident that these technologies are set to redefine the landscape of digital interaction. Each use-case presents unique challenges and opportunities, pushing the boundaries of current network capabilities and architectural designs. Enhanced detail on technical aspects, architectural impacts, and specific KPI ranges offer a comprehensive insight into the future of multimedia communications.

3.1.1 Holographic communications

Use-case description

Holographic communication [AIH22] transcends traditional video conferencing by projecting 3D, life-sized images into the air (see Figure 3-1), creating an immersive presence that mimics real-life interactions. This technology utilises principles of interference and diffraction to render images that can be viewed from any angle, making remote conversations and presentations feel as if all participants are physically present in the same room.

Figure 3-1 Holographic Communication use-case example (source Ericsson1)

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit this use-case?

SemCom enriches holographic interactions by interpreting and prioritising data based on its contextual significance, ensuring that only relevant visual and auditory information is transmitted. This results in a more focused and engaging communication experience. Goal-oriented communications refine the process further by aligning data transmission with the specific objectives of the holographic session, whether it is for educational purposes, medical consultations, business meetings, or entertainment, thereby enhancing efficiency and effectiveness.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

The architectural demands for holographic communications are significant, requiring not just high bandwidth and low latency [XPL11] [GPM20] but also advanced, often non-linear, signal processing capabilities to handle the complex wavefront reconstructions necessary for 3D hologram projection. Real-time tracking and projection adjustments based on viewer perspective necessitate dynamic resource allocation and adaptive network protocols to ensure seamless

¹ <https://www.ericsson.com/en/about-us/new-world-of-possibilities/imagine-possible-perspectives/holographic-communication/>

interaction. Architectural designs must incorporate distributed processing and edge computing solutions to minimise latency and support the computational load.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

KPIs for holographic communications include:

- *Spatial resolution:* measured in pixels per inch or PPI, with higher values indicating finer detail of the holographic image.
- *Field of view:* typically aiming for 120 degrees or more to mimic human vision.
- *Update latency:* the latency between image updating should be under 10 milliseconds to ensure real-time interaction.
- *User interaction latency:* latency between the human command and the reflected change in the hologram; targeting less than 50 milliseconds.
- *Bandwidth utilisation efficiency and hologram rendering time:* these are critical metrics for evaluating system performance, with the former optimised for minimal bandwidth consumption without sacrificing image quality, and the latter demanding rapid processing capabilities.

3.1.2 Image/Speech/Video communications

Use-case description

The realm of image, speech, and video communications is a cornerstone of modern digital interaction, underpinning a wide array of applications that range from personal communication to professional collaboration, entertainment, and education. This use-case is not just a fundamental part of network evolution; it is pivotal for societal advancements, enabling more effective and engaging ways to share information, connect with others, and understand the world around us.

Image Communications involve the transmission of still photographs or graphics across networks. High-resolution images are used in various contexts, from telemedicine [Hexa-X-II-D1.2], where detailed medical images or scans need to be shared with specialists for diagnosis, to architectural design, where detailed renderings are shared between teams. The importance of image communications has grown with the advent of social media platforms, which rely heavily on image sharing to enable users to share moments of their lives. In the realm of security, high-definition images from surveillance cameras are transmitted in real time for monitoring purposes.

Speech Communications plays a critical role in telephony, voice assistants, and speech-to-text services. It is instrumental in areas like customer service, where clear voice communication can significantly impact user satisfaction. In emergency services, reliable and clear speech communication can be lifesaving. Voice assistants and speech recognition technologies have become ubiquitous, from helping with daily tasks to providing accessibility features for those with disabilities, further underlining the societal impact of clear and reliable speech transmission.

Video Communications encompasses a broad spectrum of applications [CSS14], from video conferencing tools (see Figure 3-2) that enable remote work and education, to streaming services that offer entertainment and learning resources to a global audience. The rise of video content as a primary mode of information and entertainment highlights its importance in network traffic loads. Video streaming and conferencing have been identified as major contributors to global internet traffic, a trend that is expected to continue as resolutions increase and interactive video content becomes more prevalent.

The importance of image, speech, and video communications in the evolution of network infrastructure cannot be overstated. As the demand for higher resolutions, better audio quality, and

smoother video playback increases, network operators face the challenge of managing the significant traffic load these communications modalities impose. The evolution towards 5G and beyond is partly driven by the need to accommodate the growing demand for bandwidth and reduced latency that high-quality image, speech, and video communications require.

In defining the traffic load of network operators, video communications stand out due to their significant bandwidth requirements. As 4K and eventually 8K video become standard, and as immersive video applications such as virtual reality gain popularity, the strain on networks will only increase.

Network evolution strategies must account for these demands, ensuring that infrastructure is not only capable of handling current loads but is also scalable for future growth. This includes leveraging technologies like edge computing to reduce latency and developing more efficient data compression algorithms to manage bandwidth more effectively.

In conclusion, image, speech, and video communications are not merely use-cases for network technology; they are essential components of modern society that drive network evolution. As technology advances, the role of these communications modalities in shaping both network infrastructure and societal interaction will continue to grow, highlighting the need for ongoing investment in network capabilities to support this critical aspect of digital life.

Figure 3-2 Video Communication use-case example (source Wikipedia²)

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit this use-case?

In image, speech, and video communications, semantic technologies play a critical role in ensuring content relevance and usefulness and enhancing user engagement by analysing and understanding the content's context and the user's intent. Goal-oriented communication strategies optimise the delivery mechanisms, focusing on achieving the highest quality of experience (QoE) and perceptual quality for the given application, whether it is maximising clarity in a telehealth consultation or ensuring synchronicity in live broadcasts.

² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Videotelephony>

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

Supporting high-fidelity multimedia communications demands an architecture that not only provides sufficient bandwidth and minimal latency but also incorporates intelligent data prioritisation and error correction mechanisms to preserve content integrity across varying network conditions. Adaptive streaming technologies, robust encoding and decoding algorithms, and the capacity for real-time data compression and decompression are essential. Furthermore, the architectural design must be scalable and flexible, capable of adjusting to the ever-increasing resolution standards and evolving content formats.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

For image and video communications, critical KPIs include:

- *Resolution*: typically expressed in pixels per inch (ppi), aiming for 4K and beyond for video, and 72 ppi for displaying images on PC monitors or 300+ ppi for high quality images.
- *Frame rate*: 60 frames per second (fps) or higher is required for smooth motion in video display.
- *Bit rate*: variable, with higher rates for better quality, typically ranging from 25 Mbps for 1080p video to 100 Mbps for 4K content.

Speech communications prioritise the following KPIs:

- *Mean Opinion Score (MOS)* [SWH16]: above 4.0 for clarity and good audio quality.
- *Latency*: targeting less than 150 milliseconds for perceivable "real-time" conversation.
- *Packet loss*: should be kept below 1% to avoid noticeable degradation in quality.

3.1.3 XR (AR/VR/MR) communications

Extended Reality (XR), encompassing Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), and Mixed Reality (MR), represents a significant leap forward in how we interact with digital content. By blending the digital and physical worlds, XR technologies create immersive experiences that have applications across education, healthcare, manufacturing, and entertainment [KSO23], significantly impacting network evolution and societal interaction [Wes17] (see Figure 3-3).

Figure 3-3 XR communications use-case example (source TIM³)

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k3t4VkauM9k>

Use-case description

AR overlays digital information onto the real world, enhancing users' perceptions of their surroundings. Applications include navigation systems that project directions onto the windshield of a car, educational apps that overlay historical data onto real-world locations, and retail experiences that allow users to visualise products in their homes before purchasing. The technical aspects involve real-time image processing and spatial computing to accurately integrate digital content with the physical world, requiring high bandwidth and low latency to ensure seamless interaction.

VR immerses users in entirely digital environments, providing a sense of presence in a virtual space. Applications range from immersive gaming and virtual travel experiences to professional training simulations for surgeons and pilots. VR's technical demands include rendering high-resolution 3D environments and tracking user movement with minimal latency to prevent disorientation and motion sickness, placing significant demands on both processing power and network capacity.

MR combines elements of AR and VR to create environments where physical and digital objects coexist and interact in real time. Applications include collaborative design and engineering tools that allow users to manipulate digital models in a shared physical space, and advanced education tools that bring complex concepts to life through interactive simulations. MR's technical requirements are perhaps the most demanding, requiring not only the environmental integration of AR but also the immersive quality of VR.

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit this use-case?

SemCom ensures that XR interactions are contextually relevant, enhancing user engagement by providing information or experiences tailored to the user's environment and intent. Goal-oriented communications optimise these interactions to achieve specific outcomes, such as educational objectives in a learning app or precision tasks in a training simulation, ensuring efficiency and effectiveness in data transmission.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

The architectural requirements for XR are extensive and demanding [AG22]:

- High bandwidth to support the transmission of high-resolution textures and models, especially in VR and MR.
- Ultra-low latency to ensure real-time interaction and prevent disorientation or motion sickness in VR.
- Advanced processing capabilities for real-time rendering of complex environments and tracking user movement, necessitating edge computing solutions to minimise delays.
- Robust network infrastructure capable of dynamically allocating resources to meet the fluctuating demands of XR applications, requiring network slicing and advanced traffic management strategies.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

In the realm of XR communications, the evolution of network capabilities to support AR, VR, and MR technologies is critical. As we advance into the 6G era, the design and implementation of network infrastructure must prioritise the unique demands of these immersive technologies. To ensure a seamless and responsive user experience, specific KPIs and metrics have been identified as essential benchmarks for network performance. These KPIs not only reflect the required technical advancements but also the user expectations for immersive, real-time interactions. Below is an overview of these crucial KPIs, along with their value ranges, which are fundamental for the successful deployment of XR applications:

- *End-to-End latency:* Critical for maintaining the illusion of immediacy in XR applications, latency must be minimised to prevent user disorientation or discomfort, especially in VR. For AR and MR, the target is below 20 milliseconds, with an aspiration towards 5-10 milliseconds for applications demanding high precision. VR applications require even stricter controls, aiming for latency under 20 milliseconds to ensure immersive and nausea-free experiences.
- *Frame rate:* A smooth visual experience is essential for VR and MR applications to prevent motion sickness and maintain immersion. The frame rate should be at least 90 frames per second (fps) per eye, with some high-end systems targeting even higher rates to enhance visual fluidity.
- *Resolution:* High-resolution visuals are crucial for creating convincing and immersive XR environments. The baseline for VR applications is 1080x1200 pixels per eye, with future applications pushing towards 4K per eye to deliver lifelike detail and depth.
- *Data rate:* XR applications, with their high data throughput for real-time 3D environment rendering and interactions, necessitate large bandwidth. Basic AR applications may require a minimum of 10 Mbps, whereas more detailed and complex VR and MR content could demand bandwidth exceeding 100 Mbps to manage the data load effectively.

Addressing these KPIs in the development of 6G infrastructure is paramount to unlocking the full potential of XR technologies, enabling new forms of communication, entertainment, education, and professional applications.

3.1.4 Multi-modal communications

Use-case description

Multi-modal communications represent the convergence of various data transmission modes — such as voice, video, text, and sensory data — into a cohesive communication experience [Her15]. This integration allows users to interact with technology and each other in the most natural and intuitive ways possible, tailored to the context of their needs and environmental conditions. For example, a multi-modal system could seamlessly switch between text, voice, and video during a single conversation based on the participants' current activities, preferences, or the quality of their network connection. In a smart home environment, users could interact with devices through voice commands, gestures, and touch simultaneously, with the system understanding and responding to the most appropriate mode of communication at any given time [BMP00].

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit this use-case?

Semantic and goal-oriented communications significantly enhance multi-modal experiences by understanding the intent behind interactions and selecting the most effective communication mode for achieving the desired outcome. This involves analysing the context, such as the user's current activity, location, and the available device capabilities, to deliver information in the most accessible and impactful way. For instance, in a noisy environment, a smart device might opt to display text instead of audio for critical alerts. In educational settings, combining visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning materials could adapt to students' learning preferences, improving comprehension and retention. SemCom also enables more efficient multiplexing of multi-modality information.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

Implementing effective multi-modal communications demands a flexible and robust system architecture capable of processing diverse data types and supporting dynamic switching between communication modes. Key requirements include:

- **Advanced data processing:** Ability to analyse and interpret various data forms, including natural language, visual cues, and sensory inputs, in real time.
- **Context awareness:** Systems must understand the user context, including environmental factors and user preferences, to select the optimal communication mode.
- **Seamless integration:** Diverse communication technologies must be tightly integrated, allowing for fluid transitions between modes without user intervention.
- **Scalability and adaptability:** The architecture should easily incorporate new modalities as technologies evolve and user needs change.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

To ensure the success of multi-modal communication, several KPIs and metrics are essential:

- **Latency:** The system's response time, especially when switching between modalities, should be minimal to maintain a fluid user experience. Ideal targets are below 100 milliseconds for mode transitions.
- **Accuracy of mode recognition:** The system's ability to correctly interpret user inputs across different modalities, aiming for an accuracy rate of 95% or higher.
- **User satisfaction:** Measured through surveys or direct feedback mechanisms, indicating the ease of use and effectiveness of the multi-modal system.
- **Adaptability:** The system's capacity to adjust to new user contexts and preferences, measured by the rate of successful automatic modality adjustments.

By focusing on these aspects, multi-modal communication systems can offer more natural, efficient, and user-friendly interactions, heralding a new era of digital communication.

3.2 Task-oriented use-cases

3.2.1 Teleoperation

Use-case description

Robotic teleoperation under 5G coverage refers to the process of remotely controlling robotic systems using high-speed, low-latency communication networks provided by 5G mobile infrastructure. In this setup, human operators can manipulate robots, often equipped with sensors and actuators, from a distant location using interfaces such as joysticks, haptic devices, or even VR systems. This advanced functionality facilitates manual inspection of premises in situations such as incident responses and enables the utilization of onboard sensors for assessing critical conditions in the remote environment. Teleoperation not only enhances operational efficiency but also extends the scope of remote monitoring and evaluation in real-time scenarios.

Figure 3-4 Illustration of the semantic-aware robot teleoperation

The commands issued by the human operator are transmitted over the 5G network to the robotic system, while feedback data, including video feeds, sensor readings, and telemetry information, are relayed back to the operator in real time to ensure smooth operation.

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit this use-case?

The adoption of semantic and goal-oriented communications in the context of robotic teleoperation (under mobile radio coverage) can bring considerable benefits in terms of improved efficiency, effectiveness, and adaptability of human-robot interactions under potentially unreliable wireless communication channels.

SemCom allows human operators to convey not just commands but also the underlying intent or goals to the running robotic system. Instead of simply transmitting raw instructions, operators can provide context and meaning behind the actions they want the robot to perform. Then, the robot can interpret the commands, perform the task, and report back useful information (see Figure 3-4) For example, rather than issuing a command to a robot to "move forward," semantic communication enables the operator to specify the purpose, such as "move forward to inspect the area for potential hazards." This deeper level of understanding enables advanced robotic systems to interpret commands more accurately, as well as better plan and execute tasks in a manner better aligned with the operator's objectives. Instead of treating all commands equally, operators can convey the relative importance of different tasks, enabling the robotic system to allocate resources and effort accordingly, or the robot can prioritise commands based on local knowledge that may not be available at the remote operator. For example, in a disaster response scenario, the operator may prioritise search and rescue efforts over environmental monitoring tasks. By conveying these priorities through goal-oriented communication, the robotic system can optimise its actions to maximise the potential impact of the operation, and dynamically adapt at the environmental conditions. For instance, if a robot encounters an unexpected obstruction while navigating, it can autonomously modify its path or seek further clarification from the operator based on the overarching goal of the mission. This adaptability is crucial in complex environments where conditions may be unpredictable or evolving rapidly.

Finally, semantic and goal-oriented communication may reduce the cognitive load on human operators by providing a more intuitive and natural way to interact with robotic systems, especially when considering non-technical people. Rather than issuing low-level commands or micromanaging every aspect of the robot's behaviour, operators can focus on conveying high-level goals and objectives, allowing the robot to automatically handle the details of complex task executions, such as navigation and environment monitoring. This not only streamlines the teleoperation process but also enables operators to manage multiple robots or tasks simultaneously with greater ease and efficiency.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

The use-case requirements for the overall system design and architecture encompass several key aspects to ensure the successful implementation and operation of robotic teleoperation under mobile radio coverage:

- **Reliable wireless channel:** The system must operate over a reliable wireless channel provided by the mobile infrastructure network to ensure consistent and uninterrupted communication between the human operator and the robotic system. This entails robust signal coverage, minimal interference, and mechanisms for error detection and correction to maintain the integrity and reliability of data transmission. Additionally, the system should incorporate adaptive modulation and coding techniques to optimise performance in varying signal conditions, such as fluctuating signal strength or the presence of obstacles. By relying on a reliable wireless channel, the system can ensure continuous connectivity and seamless operation, even in challenging or dynamic environments.

- **Low-Latency communication:** The system must support reliable and low-latency communication to ensure that commands from human operators reach the robotic system without delay. Likewise, feedback and telemetry data from the robot should be transmitted back to the operator with minimal latency to maintain real-time control and situational awareness.
- **Robust security measures:** Security measures are essential to protect the integrity and confidentiality of the transmitted data, especially in applications like medical procedures or defence operations. The system should employ encryption, authentication, and access control mechanisms to safeguard against unauthorised access, tampering, or interception of sensitive information.
- **Scalability and flexibility:** The system architecture should be highly scalable and flexible to accommodate varying degrees of complexity and operational scale. It should be capable of supporting both small-scale teleoperation tasks with a single operator and robot, as well as large-scale deployments involving multiple robots and operators working collaboratively, with a large data volume of traffic flowing from the robot to the operators, e.g., video and lidar information.
- **Edge computing integration:** Integration with edge computing capabilities can enhance the system's responsiveness by offloading computational tasks closer to the point of action. This reduces latency and optimises resource utilization, particularly in scenarios where real-time processing of sensor data or decision-making is critical for mission success.
- **Redundancy and resilience:** The system should incorporate redundancy and resilience mechanisms to mitigate the risk of communication failures or network disruptions. This may include redundant communication paths, failover mechanisms, and autonomous decision-making capabilities within the robotic system to ensure continuity of operation even in challenging environments. Semantic communication is expected to bring additional capabilities to enhance the robot decision-making approaches.
- **Human-Machine Interface design:** The design of the human-machine interface (HMI) plays a crucial role in the usability and effectiveness of the teleoperation system. The HMI should be intuitive, user-friendly, and capable of providing operators with comprehensive situational awareness and control over the robotic system. Moreover, this interface can be improved by embedding semantic communication aspects into its design.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

To enable semantic-aware teleoperation several KPIs and metrics are essential:

- **Latency:** The time delay between the transmission and reception of semantic messages between Robots and operators through a dedicated wireless infrastructure. To guarantee seamless operations the communication latency has to be in the order of few tens of ms.
- **Data rate:** Target of 10-50 Mbps for most teleoperation applications with video feedback, with higher rates recommended for demanding experiences.
- **Accuracy of commands recognition:** The system requires to correctly interpret operator/user inputs across different modalities, aiming for an accuracy rate of 95% or higher.
- **Fault tolerance:** The system's ability to continue functioning correctly despite the occurrence of semantic packet loss or errors.
- **Context-awareness:** The ability of the Robot to adapt its behaviour and decision-making based on the contextual information provided through semantic communication.

3.2.2 Brain-computer interface

Use-case description

Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) enable direct communication between the human brain and an external device, typically a computer or a robotic system [He20]. BCIs can interpret neural signals and translate them into commands that allow a user to control devices or interact with the digital environment without using traditional motor pathways.

Figure 3-5 Illustration of the semantic-empowered BCI.

BCIs hold immense promise and necessitate investigation due to their potential to revolutionise multiple fields and significantly enhance the quality of life. BCIs can provide novel communication and control methods for individuals with severe disabilities, offering new ways to interact with their environment and improving their independence. In medical and rehabilitation settings, BCIs facilitate neurorehabilitation and the recovery of motor functions in stroke patients and those with neurological disorders. Moreover, BCIs can create more intuitive human-computer interactions, advance people’s understanding of brain function, and drive interdisciplinary innovation across neuroscience, computer science, and engineering. With applications ranging from mental health treatments to enhanced assistive technologies, BCIs represent a critical area for ongoing research and development, promising transformative impacts on society and individual well-being.

BCIs is a multidisciplinary research area, including neuroscience, engineering, computer science, and user-centred design. From the system design perspective, it contains the following four major sectors:

- **Signal acquisition:** This involves capturing brain signals using techniques like electroencephalography (EEG), magnetoencephalography (MEG), or invasive methods such as implantable electrodes.
- **Signal processing:** The acquired signals are filtered and analysed to extract meaningful patterns.
- **Translation algorithm:** This converts the processed signals into commands that a computer or device can understand.
- **Feedback:** The system often provides feedback to the user to improve the accuracy and control of the BCI.

So far, every above actor has had some challenges to address. The most significant one lies in signal acquisition and processing. In signal acquisition, issues such as environmental noise, physiological artifacts (like blinking or muscle activity), and the limited spatial resolution of non-

invasive techniques like EEG complicate the capture of clean neural signals. Invasive methods, while offering higher resolution, pose surgical risks and long-term health concerns. Signal stability can be compromised by electrode shifts and user variability in anatomy and neural patterns. In signal processing, extracting meaningful features from complex and noisy neural signals in real time demands advanced and efficient algorithms. Accurate classification and translation of these signals into actionable commands require adaptable systems that can handle the variability and complexity of brain activity. Additionally, reducing computational load and latency is crucial for responsive BCI applications, while effective user training and feedback mechanisms are necessary to enhance user control and system performance.

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit this use-case?

Potentially, applying semantic and goal-oriented communication into BCIs can significantly enhance their performance and usability. SemCom enables BCIs to focus on specific tasks, improving efficiency and accuracy by prioritizing relevant neural signals and providing personalised feedback. Meanwhile, SemCom enhances the BCI's ability to understand the context and intent behind neural signals, allowing for more natural and meaningful interactions [Chen16]. Eventually, by combining SemCom, BCIs can execute tasks more robustly and adaptively, providing a more satisfying and effective user experience. The SemCom models are expected to be deployed in the signal acquisition/processing and algorithm translation stages, respectively (Figure 3-5)

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

The integration of SemCom and BCIs is an innovation at the application level. The actual linkage between the BCIs and the network is loose as BCIs can purely act as a local application that has no dependencies on networks. However, the potential of BCI extension to the large-scale network level is still valid, for remote or centralised/distributed operations of BCI. In this case, the network system also needs to process the semantic BCI information in a real-time, which requires seamless cooperation and coordination of the semantic components/pipelines in the network.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

To enable effective BCI use-cases, several KPIs and metrics are essential:

- *Accuracy*: Including the classification accuracy and error rate for the given brain signals.
- *Response time*: The time it takes for the BCI to process a brain signal and execute the corresponding command.
- *Information Transfer Rate (ITR)*: A measure that combines accuracy and speed, typically expressed in bits per minute, indicating how quickly and accurately information is communicated through the BCI [Yuan13].
- *Consistency*: The ability of the BCI to maintain stable performance over time and across different sessions or scenarios.
- *Robustness*: The system's ability to perform accurately in the presence of noise and artefacts.
- *Semantic-assisted personalization*: The BCI's ability to adapt to individual user characteristics and preferences by assistant of the semantic information, enhancing performance and user experience over time.
- *Flexibility*: The capability of the BCI to be used in various applications and contexts according to the customised semantic information, demonstrating its versatility.

3.2.3 Semantic-enabled autonomous driving

Use-case description

Autonomous driving technology leverages advanced sensors, AI, and ML to enable vehicles to operate without human intervention. The integration of 5G technology significantly enhances the capabilities of Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) by providing ultra-low latency, high data throughput, and reliable communication.

Figure 3-6 Illustration of semantic-enabled autonomous driving use-case

AVs benefit from enhanced real-time communication enabled by 5G. The low latency provided by 5G networks allows AVs to process and respond to sensor data almost instantaneously. Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication, including Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V), Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I), and Vehicle-to-Pedestrian (V2P), allows AVs to share information about their surroundings and coordinate movements with other vehicles and infrastructure, enhancing safety and traffic flow. Additionally, 5G connectivity facilitates edge computing, where data is processed closer to where it is generated, reducing the time it takes to analyse sensor data and make driving decisions, e.g., continuous updating and downloading of high-definition maps, ensuring AVs have the most current information for accurate navigation. At the same time, AVs can share sensor data with nearby vehicles to create better understanding of the environment, enhancing their ability to predict and respond to potential dangers.

How semantic and goal-oriented communications benefits this use-case?

SemCom will considerably enhance transmission efficiency by exploring and only transmitting semantic information. SemCom focus on the meaning and context of the transmitted information, rather than just the raw data. In the context of autonomous driving, SemCom enable AVs to share and interpret data in a way that is more aligned with human understanding and decision-making processes. For example, when approaching an intersection (see Figure 3-6), an AV can exchange semantically rich information from/to the infrastructure, such as "traffic light turning red in 10 seconds" or "vehicle approaching from the left street at 50 km/h." This allows the AV to share in a fast way large amount of information, anticipating changes and responding more effectively even to unexpected conditions, improving safety and navigation accuracy.

In a dynamic driving environment, the priorities of an AV can change rapidly, and AV need to prioritise the data they need based on real-time conditions. A semantic-aware AV can understand and respond to contextual information, such as road signs, traffic signals, and gestures from pedestrians, leading to more natural and intuitive interactions, similar to how human drivers interpret and react to their surroundings. This will also positively affect the explainability of generally closed AI/ML models, a fact that has limited their applicability in real world settings in the recent years.

By aligning communications with specific goals, AVs can optimise the use of network and computational resources. For instance, an AV can selectively transmit high-priority data to edge computing nodes for real-time processing, while less critical data can be processed locally or transmitted at a lower priority. This ensures that the most important information is handled with the highest urgency, improving overall system performance.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

Designing a system for autonomous driving integrated with 5G technology involves several critical requirements to ensure safety, efficiency, reliability, and scalability. These requirements span across hardware, software, communication protocols, and system integration.

To achieve seamless and safe semantic-aware autonomous driving, the overall system architecture must process data in real time and communicate with minimal latency. 5G networks are key enablers to achieve this task, providing the necessary low-latency communication infrastructure, including edge computing platforms, and high-speed data processing units in the RAN and edge domains.

At the same time, AVs rely on multiple sensors (lidar, radar, camera sensors) to perceive the environment. The system must integrate and fuse data from these sensors to create a coherent and accurate environmental model, and all these data should be analysed and interpreted in a real-time manner by semantic-aware modules, to be able to extract only the most meaningful information to be forwarded to other interested parties. This step could be aided by advanced AI and ML models.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

To enable the AV use-cases, several KPIs and metrics are essential:

- *Fault tolerance:* The system's ability to continue functioning correctly despite the occurrence of faults or errors.
- *Communication latency:* The time delay between the transmission and reception of semantic messages between AVs, infrastructure, and other entities.
- *Carbon emissions:* The amount of carbon emissions produced by the AV and related data processing during operation.
- *Redundancy effectiveness:* The ability of redundant systems to maintain functionality and safety in the event of component failures.
- *Semantic data relevance:* The percentage of transmitted data that is semantically meaningful and relevant for decision-making.
- *Semantic interpretation accuracy:* The accuracy of the AV's interpretation of semantically rich information received from other entities in the vehicular network.

3.2.4 Collaborative robotics (robot-robot & human-robot)

Use-case description

Collaborative robotics typically involves multiple robots working together or with humans towards a common goal, such as the transport of goods, assembly of products, shared manipulation tasks, or coordinated navigation through dynamic environments. As pointed out in [Hexa-X-II-D1.2], the purpose of communication is to enable safety and cooperation, thanks to which robots and humans are able to perform tasks that would be not possible to perform with their individual capabilities and local data. However, large data exchange is needed for this purpose. Then, the successful execution of tasks by collaborative robotics relies heavily on effective communication among robot nodes [LA23]. This communication encompasses various types of information exchange, including task allocation and coordination, formation control

[TAPS20], sharing sensor data, exchanging position and location information, providing status updates, and detecting and recovering from errors.

Figure 3-7 Illustration of the collaborative robotics use-case

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit this use-case?

Goal-oriented and SemCom play a crucial role in enhancing collaborative robotics communication capabilities. They allow collaborative robotics to exchange information in a manner that is more meaningful and easier to interpret, thereby facilitating smoother collaboration. Moreover, from a communication perspective, goal-oriented and SemCom reduce overhead and conserve spectrum usage, optimizing the efficiency of the communication network supporting collaborative robotics operations.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

In one service area, the operational objectives and policies of collaborative robotics are expected to be controlled by a centralised controller, while direct data exchange between robot nodes occurs locally. This setup necessitates two key requirements for the overall system design: firstly, the centralised controller and in-robot processors must possess the capability to understand and process semantic information. This involves cross-layer decisions on how to split computing loads (e.g., DNN splitting) to achieve the goal of collaboration with minimum cost. This use-case is illustrated in . The O-RAN architecture provides a promising solution to implement necessary functions for end-to-end semantic processing capabilities.

Secondly, for the local robot nodes on-site, a semantic codec must be implemented to facilitate targeted semantic task execution. This ensures that the exchange of semantic information among robot nodes is seamless and efficient, guaranteeing the overall performance and collaboration of the collaborative robotics system. Distributed computing resources deployed at the different nodes of the network are also fundamental to enable agents and robots to encode and decode semantic and task-oriented information, but also increase the degrees of freedom in selecting the split of computation, based on time-varying availability of communication and computing resources.

Another requirement pertains to the capability of the network of simultaneously hosting different task-oriented use-cases using the same physical resources. In this regard, goal-oriented resource allocation and sharing can provide an additional degree of flexibility towards reduced goal cost [MFG23].

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

The KPIs and metrics to do with this use-case include communication overhead, latency, synchronicity, and task completion time, which are detailed as follows:

- *Communication overhead:* The communication overhead refers to the consumption of valuable network bandwidth, processing power, and energy resources. These KPIs can be used to assess the performance of semantic and goal-oriented communication in the collaborative robotics use-case.
- *Latency:* In this case, latency specifically refers to the data processing and transmission latency of adopting semantic and goal-oriented communication framework for collaborative robotics tasks. This includes inference latency of data collected by sensors and/or robots.
- *Synchronicity (referring to consensus):* It refers to the coordination and synchronization of actions among multiple robots or between robots and humans. Semantic and goal-oriented communications offer a meaningful interpretation of the raw information. This can improve the synchronicity among robot nodes.
- *Task completion time:* It refers to the duration taken for a specific task or set of tasks to be successfully accomplished by the collaborative robotics system. Semantic and goal-oriented communications are able to improve this time so as to maximise the throughput and overall performance of collaborative robotics systems.
- *Communication reliability:* It refers to the successful transmission of data packets.
- *Positioning accuracy:* It refers to the accuracy of information related to the location of a specific robot/agent/human, at all other collaborative robots and the network.
- *Inference accuracy:* It refers to the correct interpretation of data, including classification. In fact, successful task completion may strongly depend on a sequence of sub-tasks. In this regard, inference accuracy is then needed to guarantee correct sub-task completion.

3.2.5 Semantic-enabled edge inference

Use-case description

Edge inference, also known as edge AI inference, refers to the process of performing AI computations, such as data analysis and ML model execution, directly on devices at the edge of the network rather than in centralised cloud servers. To be specific, edge inference offers numerous advantages by processing data locally on devices rather than relying on centralised cloud servers. This approach significantly reduces latency, enabling real-time data processing and decision-making, which are crucial for applications like AVs and industrial automation. It enhances bandwidth efficiency by minimizing data transmission, leading to cost savings, and bolsters privacy and security by keeping sensitive data on local devices. Edge inference supports scalability through distributed processing and load balancing, improves reliability by enabling offline operation and fault tolerance, and optimises energy efficiency, essential for battery-operated devices. Additionally, it leverages local context for more accurate decision-making, enhances user experience with faster responses and personalised services, and helps comply with data localization regulations. These combined benefits make edge inference a compelling solution for a wide range of real-time, privacy-sensitive, and resource-efficient applications.

Figure 3-8 Illustration of image/video retrieval problem at the wireless edge.

The edge inference has many applications, such as 1) smart home devices where home automation systems can perform tasks such as voice recognition, image processing, and anomaly detection locally; 2) Industrial IoT where edge inference can be used in manufacturing and industrial environments for predictive maintenance, quality control, and real-time monitoring of equipment and processes; 3) smart cities where edge inference enables applications like real-time video analytics for security, traffic management, etc. (Figure 3-8 shows a general example).

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit this use-case?

Edge inference significantly enhances semantic and goal-oriented communications by providing low-latency, context-aware, and secure data processing. For SemCom, edge inference allows local devices to interpret and process data within the local context, enabling a deeper understanding of the semantic meaning, which improves the relevance and accuracy of the communication. By extracting and transmitting only meaningful information, it reduces data transmission, saving bandwidth and reducing network congestion. Furthermore, local data interpretation minimises the need to transmit sensitive information, enhancing privacy and security. For goal-oriented communications, edge inference facilitates real-time decision-making by offering immediate responses and enabling proactive actions, which are critical for timely goal attainment in applications like autonomous systems and emergency responses. It also optimises resource usage by ensuring that communication is focused on achieving specific goals and by processing data locally to determine the most relevant information to share. Additionally, edge devices can operate independently, making decisions without relying on constant cloud connectivity, crucial for functioning in remote or unstable network environments. This autonomy and the ability to quickly adapt to changing conditions enhance the flexibility and responsiveness of the system, making edge inference a powerful tool for effective and reliable communication in dynamic and resource-constrained environments.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

Designing a wireless communication system to support edge inference involves integrating robust edge device capabilities with sufficient processing power, memory, and storage to efficiently run AI models locally. The network infrastructure must support low latency, high bandwidth, and reliable connectivity to enable real-time processing and decision-making. Effective data management requires local processing and efficient caching to reduce latency, while strong security measures such as data encryption, access control, and anonymization protect sensitive information. The system should use standardised protocols to ensure interoperability and support integration with various devices and services. Scalability and flexibility are essential, allowing the architecture to accommodate a growing number of devices and adapt to changing requirements. Energy efficiency is achieved through power management and resource optimization, extending the battery life of edge devices. AI models need to be optimised using

techniques like pruning and quantization, with capabilities for on-device training and adaptation. Quality-of-Service (QoS) mechanisms prioritise critical data, ensuring the system meets specific latency and throughput requirements.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

The KPI and metrics related to edge inference include latency, throughput, user experience, scalability, energy efficiency, reliability, and security and privacy, which are detailed as follows:

- *Latency:* It includes inference latency and end-to-end latency. For the inference latency, the time it takes for an edge device to process data and produce an inference result. For the end-to-end latency, the total time from data generation to the final decision or action, including communication and processing delays.
- *Throughput:* It includes inference throughput and data throughput. The inference throughput stands for the number of inferences an edge device can perform per unit of time. The data throughput denotes the volume of data processed by the edge device per unit of time.
- *User experience:* It includes two parts. The first part is time perceived by the user from input to response. The second part is the subjective measure of user satisfaction with the performance of the edge inference system.
- *Scalability:* The ability of the system to maintain performance levels as the number of edge devices increases.
- *Energy efficiency:* By leveraging low-power components, optimizing AI models, minimizing data transmission, consolidating resources, and implementing energy-aware algorithms, organizations can reduce energy consumption, extend battery life, and enhance the sustainability of edge computing deployments.
- *Reliability:* By implementing robust mechanisms for system stability, data integrity, monitoring, redundancy, failover, high availability architecture, network resilience, fault recovery, and disaster recovery, organizations can minimise downtime, prevent data loss, and maintain uninterrupted service delivery in edge computing environments.
- *Security and privacy:* It requires comprehensive measures to protect against unauthorised access, data breaches, and privacy violations. By implementing encryption, access controls, secure communication protocols, privacy-preserving techniques, and compliance frameworks, organizations can mitigate security and privacy risks and build trust with users regarding the handling of their data in edge inference environments.

3.3 Network management use-cases

3.3.1 Digital twins

Use-case description

Digital twin for mobile radio systems

In mobile radio systems, digital twins (DTs) are key enablers for increasing energy and cost efficiencies, simplifying network operation, improving performance, and reducing deployment time. Usually developed for estimating the system performance, at the radio level, DTs allow the optimization of thousands to millions of parameters to improve the data rate and spectral efficiency achieved by the system (a general view is illustrated in Figure 3-9). Furthermore, they can be utilised at the RAN infrastructure and core network to evaluate, for example, the impact of new user equipment (UE) profiles, applications, or network policies before provisioning or configuring them in physical systems [Nguyen21].

Building a DT for a mobile radio system requires information on, e.g., the network topology and data traffic, characteristics of the UEs, existence of different communication flows, and interactions among the many network components. These inputs are required for estimating the system KPIs and, principally, evaluating the impact on them caused by changes in the system's parameters. With such a large number of inputs and the high complexity of current mobile radio networks, building a DT with acceptable computational efficiency requires utilizing ML methods, mixing synthetic and collected real data for training.

Another perspective of DTs is integrating their prediction capabilities with the system runtime connected to the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) for the RAN and the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) [Rahman21] in the core network. Adding such capability to predict the impacts of parameters, policies, or whatever changes in the network configuration, can prevent negative outcomes, such as degradation of the network performance, QoS, or energy consumption, after deploying these changes on the physical system [Lin23].

Figure 3-9 Radio Network digital twin high-level view

Digital twin for general monitored systems

A DT can also be a simulation process for monitored systems, such as an industrial process, an environmental system, or a transportation network. This use-case needs to be considered, as soon as the observed data of this system are transmitted to the DT data repository, training or validation function through the mobile radio network. In case of using ML for building the digital twin, the amount of data can be huge, increasing significantly the energy consumption.

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit this use-case?

Using semantics for digital twin training itself

Building a DT is a process that can require semantic modelling, especially when the purpose is to profile a simulation of an overall system aggregating various areas of technologies, processes, infrastructures, and application domains. For example, semantics, when considered as a mapping between entities based on meaning, can be assimilated in some contexts to topologies for being used by graphical models. On a communication system, this can also imply to use of the semantics of the information transmitted inside the observed system as an entry of the DT model. By including a harmonised view of the interactions and the knowledge of the

transmitted information inside the system at the semantic level, one expected benefit is a better characterization of the dependencies and correlations between the different system variables, and parameters which consist of a DT signature.

As a complementary capability, semantic and goal-oriented technologies can be used to characterise functional or physical components at different subsystems levels. The result of those characterizations is the communication to the other subsystems or an aggregation function to complete the view at the overall system layer. This consolidated description of the system can be used for the cloning process. For such “distributed or federated” ways of training a digital twin, SemCom is the proper vehicle to facilitate such models’ exchanges not only in the radio link but also between the different modules being part of the twin modelling process.

Using SemCom for digital twin applied to a radio mobile network.

The capabilities exposed above are applicable for collecting semantic properties of the different subsystems or layers that compose a radio network. In such cases, semantic information related to a UE, RAN, core network, or application behaviour can be computed by semantic modules running on each subsystem. The output of this semantic transformation can be sent to the DT data repository or training function and used directly as semantic input without being decoded.

Semantic-based classification can also be used to classify, for example, different types of message exchanges and simulate the associated traffic as part of the digital twin process. Synthetic data can then be generated from such semantic-based profiles and used during DT training, especially when applying ML algorithms (Figure 3-10).

Using SemCom for digital twin applied to general monitored systems.

Finally, SemCom can be the transmission mode used to carry observations not only related to the radio communication system itself but also associated with general monitored systems. In such a case, the semantic information transmitted through the radio for digital twin training can come from a fleet of sensors and more advanced observation devices located on the physical system. Accordingly, the transmission will benefit from the general advantages of SemCom, without receiving specific gains related to the digital twin objective per se. As for the use-cases above, the semantic data received for digital twin training do not need to be necessarily decoded if the purpose is to use such data at the semantic layer. In summary, when measurements of the physical system are needed for updating a digital twin, semantic data compression has the potential of reducing drastically the data volume to be transmitted from sensor and other monitoring equipment.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

Using semantic communication for Digital twin applied to a radio mobile network.

Having DT training and prediction capability embedded in the system runtime requires a semantic-based training function running at a location that depends on the area scope addressed by the DT operations. This function can be located on the non-real-time RIC, if the observed system is the RAN only; it can be also placed on the NWDAF or a specific Application Function (AF) collaborating with this analytic/AI function, if it concerns, for example, the overall users’ mobility or some impact estimates on the core network itself. It can also be included on the Operation Administration and Maintenance (OAM) side when decisions associated with the DT output concerned orchestration parameters or network deployment topology changes.

In the case of a more “distributed or federated” digital twin training framework, it requires specific semantic modules to get the semantic properties of each subsystem from its local data such as registered components properties, generated logs and events, or information from the subsystem observability. The purpose here is to deploy the semantic modules on different parts of the network, such as: at the UE for collecting user device context data; at the real-time RIC for radio environment characterization aspects; at the NWDAF for the core network items; at an AF for a

specific application behaviour; or, at OAM level for considering insights coming from the supervision and orchestration layers.

The deployment of those semantic modules from the very edge to the cloud implicitly means the use of SemCom for encoding/decoding data to exchange. This becomes an advantage in terms of resources and energy consumption compared to existing frameworks such as current performance management frameworks.

Figure 3-10 Semantic components for Radio Mobile system twin training

What KPI and metrics are relevant for this use-case?

The KPI and metrics related to DT are detailed as follows:

- **Accuracy:** Any KPIs allowing the assessment of a digital twin accuracy between its predicted values from a set of parameters and the effective measures after applying them on the live system. This depends on the type of prediction achieved by the DT. Semantic and goals usage processing can have a direct impact on this DT accuracy.
- **Accuracy variance:** A KPI reflecting the accuracy variance of the digital twin results. As a DT can be considered a continuous process of reassessing the representation of the model based on the latest changes or new measures collected on the physical system, its accuracy can fluctuate which can impact the reliability of its prediction over time. Semantic and goals usage processing can have a direct impact on the accuracy variance.
- **Response time:** A KPI reflecting the response time of the DT in different terms. First, the time for delivering new predictions when requested, and, secondly, the time for the DT to be up to date based on the latest configuration changes or new measurements on the observed system. As for accuracy, a response time variance as digital twin reactivity

time can vary during its lifetime depending on changes applied to the model during time. This can be an important meeting if the DT is coupled with a decision process with timing constraints. Semantic and goals usage processing can have a direct impact on this DT response time and response time variance.

- *Energy efficiency:* Energy efficiency increases the ratio between a semantic modeling at the edge and one execution at the side using non semantic communication for collecting DT inputs.

3.3.2 Personalised content generation services

Use-case description

This use-case represents the combination of the advanced generative AI with the goal-oriented and SemCom paradigm, for the purpose of offering personalised content generation services over networks.

Generative AI involves techniques that generate new data instances, such as images, text, or sounds, by leveraging patterns learned from existing data. Generative models include autoencoders, generative adversarial networks (GANs), and diffusion models, for modality generation [Cao24]. More recently, the large language models (LLMs) have achieved significant success in the context of understanding and generation. Today, significant strides have been made beyond text-to-text generation, to text-to-image, and even text-to-video generation.

The combination of SemCom and generative AI would boost the power of SemCom for modality generation, task, and context understanding. In SemCom, the information is encoded into a latent space by an encoder in a condensed format and then reconstructed by a decoder. Any of the aforementioned generative models can serve as the encoder/decoder pair. In other words, SemCom extended the flexibility and capability of generative AI to the network level. Such a combination is expected to facilitate novel SemCom applications in different layers, for instance, the physical layer and network layer. The use-case described in this section is about leveraging the SemCom and generative AI to provide personalised content-generation services, for diverse users with different preferences [Liu24].

Figure 3-11 Semantic communication for personalised content generation services

As shown in Figure 3-11, the generative model is installed in the user equipment, which is able to take the semantic representation over a radio channel as the input, as it is paired with the semantic encoder model on the RU side, which is supported natively by the semantic-aware O-RAN architecture. This generative AI can generate content or services differently according to the preference of the UE. For the generative model, this process inevitably involves the human value's collection and alignment, which in turn, results in the fine-tuning of the generative

models. Meanwhile, this process should not breach the correlations between the SemCom encoder and generative model, to ensure the semantic information can be interpreted correctly and completely.

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit these use-cases?

In this use-case, semantic and goal-oriented communications play the roles of raw information compression and semantic information extraction, which could decrease the volume of data transmission and reduce bandwidth consumption significantly. The uniqueness of this use-case lies in the functions of the semantic decoder. It employs the generative models for personalised service/content generation, which expands the flexibility of service/content delivery on the UE side.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

The implementation of this use-case put forward three requirements for overall system design and architecture. Firstly, the semantic model deployment should be supported in the RAN architecture. Ideally, on the RU unit of RAN. Secondly, the training and validation of the semantic encoder/decoder should be implemented in two loops, due to the asymmetric architecture of these two neural networks, and the interoperability of these two segments should be validated comprehensively. This asymmetric architecture raised challenges for the model's life cycle management, such as the model's updating and fine-tuning. That should be considered in the service management and orchestration of semantic-aware RAN.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for these use-cases?

The relevant KPI and metrics applicable to personalised content generation services are:

- **QoS:** This KPI refers to the level of user satisfaction with the service, specifically focusing on the satisfaction with the generated information from generative AI models in this use-case.
- **Modality fidelity:** This metric reflects the quality of modal generation. Depending on the different modalities generated by generative AI, there are various measurement indicators. For text generation, metrics such as Bilingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) and Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation (ROUGE) can be used, while for image generation, it could be Peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), etc.
- **Latency:** This is a typical metric for measuring performance in communication systems, representing end-to-end latency in this use-case. This delay should take into consideration data semantic compression and modality generation.
- **Bandwidth:** This KPI measures the reduced bandwidth consumption achieved by employing SemCom.

3.3.3 Semantic state representation for an intent-based network management

Use-case description

The core network is the “brain” of a mobile network and handles functionalities like user authentication and authorization, control signalling, data session establishment, network slice management, QoS policies, and mobility. Such functionalities belong to various distinct logical and operational domains and involve a very heterogeneous set of virtual and physical infrastructural components. As a system, the core network spans through numerous implementation layers, among which we find the (non-radio) physical layer through which data packets are transported, the virtualisation layer, the control layer, the user and network function data layer, and the management layer. All of these layers and the components that support their operations can be associated with or generate information: a broad and heterogeneous set of metrics, functional logs, performance indicators, state descriptors, and control parameters, which fully characterise

the network status at any given moment in time. Such pieces of data, though, are often incommensurable, belong to different domains, and may be correlated but not always comparable. In this context, the absence of a “holistic” view of this global network information at the core network level, prevents the optimal management of network resources (in terms, for instance, of energy efficiency, maximization of users’ QoE, or minimization of service interruptions). Such a holistic approach may be achieved by translating all gatherable data into a novel *semantic representation of network states*, with the support of AI-based tools, embedded in existing intelligent core network components, like the 5G NWD AF, or new dedicated ones. In this framework, we propose to define a new core network functionality called the Semantic State Repository Function (SSRF). It may be realised as an independent function or as a sub-functionality that extends the current capability of the NWD AF. We provide some more detail on the architectural requirements for the deployment of the SSRF in [D2.2]. The proposed SSRF, depicted as an independent core network function in Figure 3-12, acts as a semantic aggregator of network states collected from the other core network functions (and, possibly, by them from other network components such as the RAN). Such aggregation of data is carried out with a threefold goal: efficiently reducing the overall volume of the gatherable useful data and processing it to ensure that it is afterward understandable, analysable, and available in a unified language to network and external components (e.g., an orchestrator, an AF, a human network administrator).

Examples of heterogeneous information are logs and counters of Non-Access Stratum (NAS) control messages exchanged between a portion of the UEs and the Access and mobility Management Function (AMF), Session Management Function (SMF) session logs, and network performance metrics. They are all correlated with an actual user’s QoE and with its utilization of the network’s connectivity services, but they can provide tangible and exploitable insight into the latter only after being correlated via an end-to-end cross-layer analysis. This analysis is far from trivial, cannot be made “at a glance” by simply looking at the charts on a network administrator’s dashboard, and requires an advanced analytic system. To this end, the first key component to obtain the targeted cross-component unified data representation (i.e., one or more elements’ *semantic state*) is the use of advanced algorithms and semantic analysis techniques. These have the power to transform heterogeneous data from various sources into comprehensible and coherent semantic data. For instance, through LLM-based analysis, we can identify patterns and anomalies in the raw data and make them understandable and usable for a network administrator, fostering a deeper comprehension of the network behaviour. This analysis can then be translated into a semantic state, defined as the set of “encoded” information in a language format that reconstructs the original state of the network function into a uniform standardised representational form.

For example, consider the following heterogeneous collection of data: $X = \{\text{an increase in NAS message counters indicating potential congestion in the AMF; SMF session logs revealing frequent session drops; network performance metrics indicating high user-plane latencies}\}$. By applying advanced algorithms and LLM-based analysis, these disparate pieces of information can be translated into a coherent semantic state Y , such as $Y = \text{“unreliability of network connectivity services due to gNB congestion”}$. The challenge lies in encoding X into Y in a manner that: i) is representative of an actual network condition; ii) is readable by both an external orchestrator and a human administrator; iii) leads to actionable decisions and network reconfigurations to optimise the network state or solve the identified problem. In other words, a semantic state provides a unified and understandable snapshot of the network’s status (or of a subset of its components), enabling efficient decision-making in a framework that is compatible with intent-based management and orchestration.

Figure 3-12 Independent core network function

For example, consider the following heterogeneous collection of data: $X = \{\text{an increase in NAS message counters indicating potential congestion in the AMF; SMF session logs revealing frequent session drops; network performance metrics indicating high user-plane latencies}\}$. By applying advanced algorithms and LLM-based analysis, these disparate pieces of information can be translated into a coherent semantic state Y , such as $Y = \text{“unreliability of network connectivity services due to gNB congestion”}$. The challenge lies in encoding X into Y in a manner that: i) is representative of an actual network condition; ii) is readable by both an external orchestrator and a human administrator; iii) leads to actionable decisions and network reconfigurations to optimise the network state or solve the identified problem. In other words, a semantic state provides a unified and understandable snapshot of the network’s status (or of a subset of its components), enabling efficient decision-making in a framework that is compatible with intent-based management and orchestration.

In particular, the second targeted component is the inclusion in the proposed solution of intent mechanisms, present in the literature [MAA24] and in ETSI specifications too [ETSI128312]. More precisely, we target to associate the human-readable semantic state information elaborated by the SSRF with potential actions that could be also triggered by a semantic orchestrator engine (through a network’s management interfaces) or by an external Application Function (leveraging the “classical” 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) interfaces exposed by, e.g., the NWDAF or the Network Exposure Function (NEF)). An intent-based manager and orchestrator would then be able to control the network using commands expressed in the same language as the network states, addressing use-cases such as i) network function monitoring and anomaly detection; ii) load balancing; iii) fault tolerance and reliability.

The target is relying on intents that serve as high-level machine-readable specifications that encapsulate business goals, requirements, and constraints, enabling autonomous network management. These intents dynamically adapt to changing business objectives and are goal-oriented, focusing on what needs to be achieved rather than on how to achieve it. Each intent is represented by a base utterance, which can be a phrase, a word, or even a partial word. These bases linked to intents are essential for a smooth transition from user inputs to actionable commands or decisions that influence the semantic states of the network. These states, represented in the SSRF, share the same language as utterances thus ensuring comprehensive understanding and processing of user inputs, enhancing system coherence and functionality. Within this family of intents, considering also the previously listed use-cases, we can identify

three main types of intents: i) Monitoring Intent, ii) Load Balancing Intent, and iii) Resilience Intent.

For instance, a “Monitoring Intent” might be expressed as the utterance “Provide me the UPF status,” which considers a set of metrics specific to a network function such as the User Plan Function. An example from the “Load Balancing Intent” type is the intent triggered by the utterance “Reconfigure the user-equipment-to-gNB association via the AMF to address performance issues caused by high loading.” This directive could be triggered by a semantic orchestrator engine or administrator user interface when the network’s status highlights some kind of suboptimality or underperformance. In our example, the system detects the access network’s high load via the information available at the AMF (and/or SMF, UPF, etc.) and gathered via the SSRF and exposed to the external orchestration component. In a closed and automated control loop, the latter autonomously adjusts the mobile network configuration to balance the load, thereby improving overall performance. In addition, network states, utterances, and intents are all understandable by a human administrator.

A final example involves the “Resilience Intent” type; if the QoS is not guaranteed for a group of users over a certain period, a command like “Change QoS for users in slice S” can prompt a response to adjust their associated profiles in the UDR. For example, if users in a particular slice are experiencing degraded service due to network congestion, the system can dynamically adjust its QoS settings to prioritise critical services, ensuring a more consistent user experience.

Finally, to enhance prompt variability, LLMs can transform initial prompts. By generating prompts with different seeds, we introduce linguistic diversity while preserving the original semantic meaning. For example, the initial utterance “Give me the UPF status” could be transformed into “Provide the current status of the UPF” or “What is the UPF status now?” This not only maintains the intent and meaning but also provides flexibility in how requests can be understood and processed by the system. This approach not only optimises data management but also ensures coherent and actionable insights across the network.

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit these use-cases?

Understanding large volumes of data is a major challenge in today’s world. Semantic and goal-oriented communication is particularly important for this purpose, as it enables the system to reduce information overload and enhance interpretation. Traditional systems often exchange raw data, which sometimes are useless due to the large number of features required to describe the system or part of it. By implementing semantic and goal-oriented tools, which are also multi-modal, networks, such as in the case of the 5G, we can manage another level of abstraction that is more comprehensive and reusable. In this context, each component of the network can exchange information in a more human-like manner, potentially optimizing the network in terms of the resources required while also minimizing energy consumption by conserving these.

The proposed SSRF is designed to reduce data volume and provide a unified language for representing the state of various network components. Through the intent mechanism, we can map this state into concrete actions (intents), which modify the network function's state based on its semantic representation. This approach not only optimises data management but also ensures coherent and actionable insights across the network.

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

Regarding functional requirements, the mobile network system must collect various data types from sources such as message counters exchanged by the AMF/SMF and logs, performance indicators, state descriptors, and control parameters. These data elements provide a comprehensive snapshot of the network status at any given time. This heterogeneous set of data must be transformed to represent the semantic states set, within the new Core Network SSRF, representing the behaviour of each network function in a human-readable way. At the same time,

semantic orchestrators and application functions are responsible for triggering, through predefined intents, actions on potential semantic states within the SSRF through the interfaces exposed by NWDAF/NEF aligning with 3GPP/ETSI technical standards. Additionally, the system must utilise LLMs to generate variable prompts ensuring consistent semantic meaning for both the network function state and the associated intent for a semantic state.

Regarding non-functional requirements, the system must ensure reliability in data analysis and interpretation. It must adapt to an increase in the number of monitored network functions without performance degradation. The system should be easy to update and maintain through update mechanisms. The system, and the introduction of the SSRF, must be compatible with other existing solutions and standards in the 5G field, integrating with various network infrastructures and technologies. In this sense, the SSRF must be developed in compliance with the service-based architecture of modern (5G and beyond) core networks. Another fundamental aspect of the system is the capability of processing data in real or near real-time to make the entire network operate at maximum performance, avoiding performance degradation due to anomalous behaviour within the network.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for these use-cases?

The most relevant metrics useful for evaluating an intent-based network, which could proactively change its behaviour according to a certain requirement, include:

- *Semantic state accuracy:* In an intent-based network, it measures the differences between original raw data values (prior to semantic translation) with the ones that are made understandable and practical for a network administrator.
- *Throughput:* Measures of how many units of information a system can process in a given amount of time. In our use-case, it could be related to the ability to process and transmit user data through the network.
- *Latency:* In an intent-based network, the exchange of information must be as fast as possible. The introduction of a new semantic AI mechanism should further improve the latency in terms of transmission.
- *Semantic similarity:* Assessing how closely answers relate in meaning can provide valuable insights into response quality. This assessment employs a cross-encoder model to determine the semantic similarity score.
- *Answer correctness:* This metric considers two elements: the semantic similarity between the produced answer and the correct answer, and the factual similarity. These elements are merged using a weighted system to determine the correctness score of the response.

3.4 IoT use-cases

Use-cases description

All IoT use-cases described below address the required trade-offs between energy consumption, coverage, and intelligence. This mainly implies offering more intelligence with less transmitted data and consequently saving energy, without impacting the achieved coverage, by offering the proper trade-off between the energy needed at the physical layer for introducing more intelligence and the energy saved by transmitting less data and still providing all the required information in terms of the actual payload. In turn, this leads to further advantages, namely extended battery lifetime for the IoT devices, reduced latency, increased data rates, and radio resource-saving at RAN level, made available to be exploited for increased IoT connection density or other services.

Use-case: Heterogeneous IoT devices

One of the key IoT scenarios is massive IoT, in which a very high density of devices, such as sensors, are deployed to monitor various physical quantities of interest, such as environmental conditions, industrial processes, etc. The devices may or may not be constrained in terms of energy, computation capabilities, etc., and may have long lifetimes. Due to the large number of devices, as well as possible energy constraints, it is infeasible for them to constantly transmit their sensor readings to the base stations (BSs). Instead, only a small subset of the devices is active and transmits observations at a time. For instance, the devices may activate periodically or be triggered by their sensor observations, possibly in combination with some condition broadcasted by the BS, such as a threshold. As a result, the set of active devices is unknown a priori to the BS, and thus their observations need to be transmitted using random access protocols.

In recent years, industrial applications have backed up classical low-data massive sensor devices with devices having high throughput requirements, and/or sensors monitoring physical quantities of a critical nature, creating the need to fulfil high throughput, low latency and/or high reliability requirements for a small subset of devices while guaranteeing the high connection density for the remaining IoT devices. This generates the need for intelligent resource slicing between heterogeneous traffic in sensor networks. In addition, the IoT traffic in 5G has been largely seen as device-initiated, that is, devices pushing data towards the networks, either sporadically or critical transmissions with low latency. For this use-case, we will generalise the setup by considering closed-loop IoT traffic, such as the one in which the intelligent nodes at the network are purposefully pulling data from the IoT devices by sending queries and thereby requesting transmissions.

Use-case: Extended coverage, medium latency, and medium data rate IoT

IoT solutions can provide radio coverage extension up to 20 dB compared to the one achievable with a reference service like General Packet Radio Service (GPRS), with an overall Maximum Coupling Loss (MCL) of 144 dB (i.e., the GPRS reference point in UL) + 20 dB = 164 dB.

This 20 dB improvement corresponds approximately to the loss that occurs when a signal penetrates not only the outer wall of a building, but also inner walls/floors/basements and metal cases devices may be protected by/located in, and thus allows for also serving devices that are placed in signal challenged locations like basements (e.g., meters) or remote rural areas. Figure 3-13 graphically shows the coverage extension of Narrowband-IoT (NB-IoT) compared to the coverage achieved with e.g., LTE-GSM for devices located in the basements like meters.

Figure 3-13 Coverage extension of IoT compared to other wireless technologies

The legacy requirement in terms of latency is of at most 10 seconds to deliver exception reports in UL at such extended coverage with MCL = 164 dB, e.g., in specific situations like smoke alarm detection, power failure notifications from smart meters, tamper notifications, etc., even though the above systems were mainly designed for less delay-sensitive applications.

The legacy requirement in terms of data rate ranges from a few tens of kbps in the case of NB-IoT up to hundreds of kbps in the case of enhanced Machine-Type Communications, a.k.a. LTE-M, in the first available 3GPP Rel-13 specifying them, depending on the considered applications and needs [3GPP36.201, 3GPP36.211, 3GPP36.212, 3GPP36.213, 3GPP36.214, 3GPP36.216].

The above high latency and low data rate requirements stem from the need for an extensive number of repetitions of the transport blocks, transmitted at the physical layer, to allow for their correct reception even in case of required extended coverage of 20 dB compared to the reference one. This leads to increased latency, reduced data rates, decreased battery lifetime, and extensive radio resource consumption.

Since IoT applications requiring extended coverage are not necessarily all featured with extremely relaxed latency and low data rate requirements, it is necessary to overcome the bottleneck introduced by the extensive repetition of the transport blocks at the physical layer, which is completely agnostic in terms of the type of information included in the transport blocks. This also leads to increased battery lifetime and optimised radio resource usage. The workaround is therefore meant to address even medium latency and medium data rate IoT applications still requiring extended coverage — but still discarding IoT applications with low latency and high data rate requirements, which are typical of mission-critical IoT applications with features like Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC) which might not be suitable in case of extended radio coverage conditions, where the further ultra-reliability feature is challenging to cope with.

The use-cases requiring extended coverage, medium latency, and medium data rate for IoT may encompass smart agriculture, soil monitoring, connected vineyard, connected e-bikes tracking, fleet tracking, asset tracking, smart grid monitoring, smart metering, and fault management for water, gas and energy utilities, wearables, and healthcare devices. Depending on the class of the considered use-case, the technology to be adopted may rely on NB-IoT or LTE-M enabled with semantic and goal-oriented communications, whose features need to be implemented at both the devices and radio network sides via semantic modules.

Use-case: Low Powered and energy-autonomous IoT devices

Low-power IoT devices are moving to mature technology, especially for a large amount of IoT domain usage. More recently the high requirements of energy consumption and associated carbon footprint reduction have increased the need for such low-power solutions from narrow to extended wideband usage.

By leveraging limited energy-consuming components at both IoT modules and radio infrastructure while improving the throughput and latency capacities of the overall solution, it becomes possible to propose end-to-end offers enabling new market perspectives as in industry 4.0. By combining sober energy-consuming modules to even autonomous powering with self-powered modules using the capacity to collect energy from solar panels or environment heat, new use-cases will raise for sustainable IoT solutions.

In LTE nowadays, Low-Power Wide-Area (LPWA) networks are mainly addressed by two transmission modes NB-IoT and LTE-M. All those protocols, by providing power-saving mode while remaining adjusted to IoT models, could be considered for a larger number of applications as soon as the amount of transmitted user data can be compressed to the available throughput. In

5G Advanced as today, NR-Light (RedCap) IoT mode supporting a lower latency and a higher throughput than LPWA protocols can also be considered for this use-case.

Figure 3-14 Illustration of LPWA IoT system with semantic/goal-oriented communications

How do semantic and goal-oriented communications benefit these use-cases?

Semantic and goal-oriented communications allow for reducing the overall amount of data to be transmitted by a single IoT device, at the physical layer, by making the transmitter as aware as possible of the information actually needed by the receiver (typically the network from the application layer down to the RAN in the protocol stack). Specifically, the information could be in terms of frequency, at update level, level of details, add-ons compared to the information already available at the receiver side, periodical time frames allocation for transmitting the expected information avoiding time and resource consuming random access procedures with contention resolution.

The above educated-guess transmissions allow for reducing the amount of transmitted data and, consequently, the number of transport blocks to be transmitted and repeated/retransmitted at the physical layer. This comes with a trade-off between a possible increased channel encoding and the reduced payload, and a consequent further reduced number of repetitions/retransmissions of the transport blocks. The semantic-empowered LPWA system (Figure 3-14) can lead to reduced latency, increasing of the achievable data rates, increasing in battery lifetime of the IoT devices and optimised percentage of used radio resources at RAN level.

Current random-access protocols are designed with the objective of maximizing the number of supported simultaneously active users, considering generic packets and/or information bits. By designing random access protocols that consider what information the receiver is interested in and how it intends to use it, the relevance of the collected information can be increased.

Semantics and goal-oriented communications can be integrated into random access in several ways. At the application layer, it can be used to, for instance, filter the devices that have data to transmit, so that only devices with relevant information activate. Similarly, at the medium access control (MAC) layer, it can be used to prioritise channel resources to device transmissions based on their semantic relevance. At the physical layer, the concept of pull-based communication mixed with the employment of wake-up received could be implemented to retrieve the readings

of interest, without wasting the energy of the sensors to transmit irrelevant information. Pull-based communication is an instance of closed-loop communication, initiated by the processing nodes at the network.

The system should exploit an intelligence-based evolution: when a device is connected to the BS to access the network, it may know neither what is relevant for the BS/edge server nor when to send it. Over time, as communication proceeds, the devices may learn about the relevance and timeliness of the data either based on the queries coming from the BS or from the explicit transmission of a learning model from the BS to the device (which would teach the device what and when to send).

What are the use-case requirements for overall system design and architecture?

Requirements for Heterogeneous IoT devices use-case

The overall requirement is for the system to be scalable to support many devices. In the most extreme cases, the total number of devices could be in the order of hundreds of thousands per km², up to reach the 3GPP massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) requirements. This entails to supporting a connection density of 1 million devices per km², even with NB-IoT and LTE-M already in 3GPP Rel-13 (2016), out of which just a small percentage of them may be active at a given time.

At the system level, the use-case can be separated into push-based and pull-based scenarios, or a mixture of the two. In the push-based scenario, the transmissions are triggered independently by each device, based on a local decision and without information from the base station. On the other hand, in the pull-based scenario, the base station transmits a signal that selects the active devices based on its goal.

To this aim, some sort of intelligence needs to be considered at the base station coordinating the transmissions and/or at the sensor devices, taking into account that a data-driven model of the physical process of interest can be stored and updated to determine the semantic relevance of the messages. Remark that the model of the physical quantities updated regularly with the collected information can be seen as a digital twin of the monitored environment, although in this use-case the timing and synchronization requirements are more relaxed.

From a communication point of view, the BS needs to be able to manipulate the MAC frame and the physical resources to accommodate the successful access of a massive number of devices coordinating the different kinds of transmission (push and pull) while possibly fulfilling heterogeneous requirements for a small subset of devices. The use of a digital twin of the monitored environment may be used to help the decisions at the frame level through the prediction of the short-term future necessities of the network.

Requirements for Extended coverage, medium latency, and medium data rate IoT use-case:

To achieve semantic and goal-oriented communications advantages, conventional technologies like NB-IoT and LTE-M need to be enabled with semantic modules at both the IoT devices and the network at different levels of the protocol stack.

One aspect that needs to be carefully considered is the energy required for semantic processing in the IoT device, taking its overall battery lifetime into account. Specifically, the energy spent by the inference model associated with the semantic model, enabled in the device, to achieve an optimised trade-off between the energy needed for the semantic processing in the IoT devices, and the energy saved at the physical layer transmission with semantic and goal-oriented communications.

To minimise the energy needed for semantic processing in the IoT devices, strategies of unbalanced splitting of semantic processing between the semantic modules in the IoT devices and the semantic modules at the network size may be considered.

A streamlined semantic module on IoT devices could significantly improve overall energy efficiency. This improvement considers not just the percentage of radio resources used at the RAN level, which might not be the optimal one, but also the energy saved across all IoT devices equipped with a simplified semantic module, resulting in longer battery life for these devices.

It is also worthwhile noting that the network (at any level where the more sophisticated semantic modules are implemented) may trigger the RAN at the physical layer to transmit the request of a message to the IoT device to provide useful up-to-date information.

Requirements for Low Powered and energy-autonomous IoT devices use-case:

LPWA modes such as LTE Cat-M1 or NB-IoT are not adapted for usage as transmitting as example images with high resolution but can transmit reasonably semantic information associated with this image to become suitable in terms of associated energy spending and so battery autonomy. By reducing the payload to semantic information, this transmission duration in the radio can be limited, leading not only to lower energy consumption but also to lower latency interaction between the IoT device and its counterpart receiver.

One restraint of such semantic communication for LPWA is to split the model inference between the IoT device and a local receiver on the infrastructure side to apply the proper energy balance between the one due to the semantic processing in the device and the one due to the transmission on the radio link. The purpose here is not only to optimise the energy consumption of the overall transmission chain but also to keep the proper level of power autonomy on the IoT module to enlarge its battery life cycle or fit its power consumption to the autonomous refuelling capacity.

What KPI and metrics are relevant for these use-cases?

The relevant KPIs and metrics common to all IoT use-cases described above may include the following ones related to semantic and goals-oriented:

- *Latency*: the time elapsing between the instant a physical process happens and the instant the appropriate reading is decoded at the base station. It takes the synchronization process, cell detection, and random-access procedure into account, besides data transmission related to the UL application payload and data reception related to the DL application ACK. For applications regarding time-critical processes, assessing and being able to operate a certain deadline is of fundamental importance. This KPI is important to measure the capability of the transmission mode to deliver or exchange information without facing blocking impacts stemming from additional AI processing duration in the communication path.
- *Radio resources saving*: percentage of radio resources saved at RAN level with the semantic and goal-oriented communications approach compared to the radio resources used in the legacy approach without it, for same configuration of the other parameters.
- *Energy saving and efficiency KPIs*:
 - *IoT device energy consumption saving*: in many applications, the energy consumption of the IoT devices needs to be kept at a minimum. This consumption should consider all the energy expended to monitor, store, code, and transmit the data as well as the energy spent by the decision process of the transmission (if one).
 - *Energy saving at RAN level*: the difference between the gain in energy saving at RAN level with semantic and goal-oriented communications approach with respect to the conventional physical layer transmission and the energy needed for the semantic processing at the RAN level.

- *Overall energy saving*: energy saving at RAN level + IoT device energy consumption saving.

The additional KPIs and metrics relevant for Heterogeneous IoT devices use-case may include the following ones:

- *Information freshness*: a specific application interested in having a digital twin of the physical processes under observation may need to update the models with fresh data. In this case, relevant metrics like age of information (AoI), query age of information (qAoI), and value of information (VoI) should be taken into account to decide which data to transmit or store.
- *Accuracy*: at the BS side, the representation of the monitored processes or the digital twin of the overall system needs to be accurate and trustworthy, that is, the accuracy of the data transmission can only be assessed in the context of the inference/model at the BS side.

The additional KPIs and metrics relevant for the Extended coverage, medium latency, and medium data rate IoT use-case may include the following ones:

- *Extended coverage*: Check compliance with the legacy 164 dB extended coverage requirement also in case of semantic and goal-oriented communications adoption. No gain is required.
- *Latency reduction*: Gain, in terms of latency reduction with semantic and goal-oriented communications, compared to the legacy latency requirement of at most 10 seconds to deliver exception reports in UL at extended coverage with MCL = 164 dB.
- *Data rate increase*: Gain, in terms of data rate increase with semantic and goal-oriented communications, compared to the achievable legacy data rate in UL at extended coverage up to MCL = 164 dB (depending on the considered technology, e.g., NB-IoT or LTE-M, with the same configurations of the other parameters used without semantic and goal-oriented communications).

The additional KPIs and metrics relevant for Low Powered and energy autonomous IoT devices use-case may include the following ones:

- *Communication overhead*: One important aspect of LPWA is the capability to maintain the device in power-saving mode with proper adaptation of radio procedure timers. The introduction of semantic and goal-oriented communication should keep those adaptations at a proper level of optimization without introducing heavy and frequent new communication overhead to support them.
- *DL/UL throughput and emission frequency capability*: The reachable throughput and messages frequency, enabled by semantic and goals-oriented communications, allow to evaluate the benefits of semantic and goals-oriented communications in terms of transmitted information capability, from the device to the receiver, while guaranteeing autonomy of the IoT device in terms of battery or recharge capacity in case of energy autonomous devices.

4 System Design Requirements

6G-GOALS aims to realise the potential of cutting-edge AI-native architectures along with new semantic and goal-oriented communication paradigms.

In light of this ambitious objective, we meticulously customise the taxonomy of requirements specifically tailored to the design of the 6G-GOALS system. This comprehensive taxonomy serves as a structured framework that outlines the essential criteria and specifications essential

for the development and implementation of cutting-edge 6G technologies and communication systems.

4.1 Taxonomy of requirements

In this taxonomy, we categorise the system design requirements into seven key areas, as depicted in Figure 4-1 architectural, functional, management and orchestration, integration and compatibility, use-case, and performance requirements. Each category of requirements embodies a critical aspect of design, contributing to the development of a comprehensive and resilient communication system.

Figure 4-1 The taxonomy of 6G-GOALS system design requirements

4.2 Architectural requirements

Architectural requirements play a pivotal role in sketch the fundamental system components and interfaces necessary to facilitate semantic awareness within the network infrastructure. These requirements serve as a blueprint for designing and implementing robust and scalable architectures capable of supporting advanced semantic capabilities. For implementing goal-oriented and semantic communication in 6G networks, enabling seamless in-network AI performing capability, the following architectural requirements have to be taken into consideration.

Semantic Understanding and Goal Orientation: The network architecture and its contained functions should be able to understand and represent the meaning of the content it interacts with, including text, images, speech, and other modalities, in a semantic manner. Meanwhile, the network should be designed to understand and pursue specific goals or objectives provided by users or defined by tasks. It should have mechanisms to interpret user intents and preferences and generate appropriate responses, actions, and decisions to achieve those goals [Li23]. The network correspondingly allocates the in-network resources as needed.

Modularity and Flexibility: The architecture should be modular, allowing for easy integration of different components and functionalities. This modularity facilitates flexibility in adapting to various tasks and domains without significant re-engineering.

Scalability and Efficiency: The architecture ought to be designed to scale with increasing data and computational resources. Meanwhile, the system's operational efficiency should be placed into the central stage of design, with the ultimate goal of reducing the energy consumption per bit in general.

Robustness and Adaptability: The network should be robust and stable in front of different deployment scenarios, such as noise, uncertainty, and adversarial inputs (e.g., to neural networks). Additionally, it should be adaptable to changes in the environment, user preferences, or task requirements without significant performance degradation.

4.3 Functional requirements

Functional requirements specify the essential functionalities needed to process semantic and goal-oriented tasks within the network. These requirements are driven by 6G-GOALS innovations across different WPs. It is important to note that some of these requirements focus on establishing the foundations of goal-oriented and semantic communication paradigms, while others emphasise the need for system enhancements to adopt this novel paradigm within the network.

Context Awareness and Semantics: The network should understand and interpret the context and semantics of the data being transmitted via a specifically designed function element, which has to be able to recognise user intents and adapt the communication strategies accordingly. Meanwhile, the network should be able to allocate resources intelligently based on the goals and priorities of the users and applications.

Analytics and Decision-Making in different time scales: For the involved semantic tasks, the network must be capable of providing timely responses according to the requested time scales, including real-time, near-real-time, and non-real-time. Coordination between cloud, network, and edge computing is essential for effective data processing and decision-making.

Time-sensitive task processing: The goal-oriented and semantic applications may also rely on many multi-sensory inputs acquired in real-time by network nodes. These inputs might be available at different times at the target nodes due to the high complexity of the digital systems and, consequently, the several aspects that affect timing. For instance, heterogeneous node specifications result in different time budgets for acquiring and processing observations from physical processes. Furthermore, the information arrivals are subject to the signal propagation delay, the data rates supported by the different communication links until the target nodes, and the general characteristics of the deployed communication protocols. For example, on the communication protocols, the coexistence of push and pull communication modes intricately ties the time to convey information to variable contention periods and multiple duty cycles. In this regard, time-sensitive tasks require the capacity of consistent temporal ordering of data at the target nodes, recovering the original chronology of the multi-sensory inputs without violating the causality and simultaneity relationships among them [P24]. To this end, there is a need for a reliable time-stamping function in the network, making it possible for every node to assign indices to the sequence of events within its responsibility. These timestamps are transmitted along with the data, enabling the recovery of the information chronology at the destination nodes. Efficient software and hardware timestamping have been proposed for multi-node clock synchronization, reaching accuracy in the nanoseconds scale [XLL21]. Combined with the Time Window of Integration (TWI) framework introduced by [P24], there is the possibility of adapting these time-stamping strategies according to the simultaneity horizon required by the applications.

Distributed reasoning and actuation tasks: Implementing distributed reasoning and actuation tasks in wireless networks demands advanced capabilities for collaborative data processing and coordinated actions among interconnected devices. The network must support edge and

fog computing to enable local data processing and reduce latency, while high-speed, low-latency communication infrastructure is essential for real-time data exchange and rapid response. Semantic communication is crucial for contextual data interpretation, allowing the network to adapt dynamically to achieve specific goals like energy efficiency or low latency. Semantic models and consensus mechanisms must be integrated to ensure synchronised and optimal performance of distributed devices.

4.4 Management and orchestration requirements

The management and orchestration (M&O) requirements outline the updated approaches for managing and orchestrating network functions and resources within the semantic-aware network.

In the state-of-the-art 5G network, M&O refers to the systems and processes used to efficiently deploy, operate, and optimise the network infrastructure and services. This involves a range of functions such as resource allocation, network slicing, automation, and real-time analytics. Orchestration coordinates the dynamic deployment of network resources and services across distributed and heterogeneous environments, ensuring seamless connectivity and performance. Management encompasses the ongoing monitoring, maintenance, and optimization of these resources. Together, they enable the flexible and scalable nature of 5G networks, allowing for rapid deployment of new services, efficient use of resources, and the ability to meet diverse requirements from various applications and user demands.

To incorporate the goal-oriented and semantic functions into the state-of-the-art network, extra M&O requirements should be satisfied to harmonise the actions of the semantic modules and the network legacy functions.

Coordination of new system components and functions: In-network semantic modules pose requirements for the coordination of new system components and functions with existing ones, which is crucial in communication systems to ensure seamless integration and interoperability. This coordination allows for the smooth transition and adoption of semantic-related technologies without disrupting current services or user experiences. Effective coordination also facilitates a unified and cohesive network operation, minimizing potential conflicts and optimizing resource utilization across the entire system. This holistic approach should ultimately lead to a more robust, scalable, and future-proof communication network.

Knowledge base synchronization and updating: The knowledge base lays the foundation of the semantic models for efficient data interpretation, knowledge sharing, and intelligent decision-making across different systems and applications. Generally, the knowledge base is used as the training data set of the semantic models. The mismatch between the semantic knowledge base and the realistic environment features will cause serious problems for the semantic models in terms of model inference. Therefore, the synchronization and updating of the knowledge base over networks is important for the semantic models to get the latest knowledge and fine-tune themselves accordingly. This synchronization and updating method should be carefully designed by considering the venue of knowledge base storage, the path of the knowledge base synchronization/updating, and how to trigger the synchronization/updating with a specific time granularity.

SemCom model's life-cycle management method: SemCom models, essentially AI/ML models, undergo a life-cycle management process within communication networks that is vital for their effective development and deployment. This systematic process typically includes several key steps: initially, meticulous planning and development stages involve identifying network requirements and tailoring AI models to address them. Subsequently, training and testing phases ensure models are equipped to learn patterns and make accurate predictions or decisions. Once deployed, continuous monitoring becomes imperative, enabling real-time assessment of model

performance and prompt anomaly detection. Maintenance and updates ensure models remain relevant and effective by incorporating new data and knowledge. Eventually, retirement or replacement decisions are made based on ongoing assessments of model effectiveness and relevance over time.

Despite the importance of this life cycle, current wireless communication networks lack a clearly defined pipeline for its execution [Li22]. While 3GPP works on AI/ML models' transfer and distribution, the comprehensive life-cycle management method for in-network intelligence remains unclear, especially for SemCom models. Alternatively, the concept and practice of ML Operations (MLOps) offer a promising solution, combining data engineering, AI/ML models, and continuous integration and delivery (CI/CD) pipelines. While MLOps suits streamlined environments and simple tasks, adapting it for in-network AI/ML model management is a burgeoning research area.

Given the unique characteristics of SemCom models, such as their knowledge base, and focus on reconstruction and fidelity, modifying existing MLOps principles to suit SemCom model requirements leads us to propose a new paradigm, SemComOps, for further exploration and study.

4.5 Integration and compatibility requirements

These requirements pertain to ensuring that the new components, interfaces, functions, and orchestration methods are not only compatible with legacy systems but also integrate seamlessly with them. This integration is crucial to maintaining system coherence and operational stability while introducing advanced capabilities. The requirements can be divided into two main parts: 1) the co-existence of SemCom components and legacy network components, and 2) the co-existence and coordination of traditional task processing capability and SemCom processing capability.

Co-existence of SemCom and Legacy Network Components: The integration must allow for the seamless operation of SemCom components alongside legacy network components. This includes ensuring that communication protocols, data formats, and interface standards are compatible across both old and new systems. Effective backward compatibility is essential to prevent disruptions in service and to leverage existing infrastructure investments.

Coordination of Traditional and SemCom Processing Capabilities: The system has to support the coordination between traditional task processing and SemCom processing capabilities. This involves creating new management/orchestration techniques that can manage the workload distribution, resource allocation, and task prioritization between these two processing paradigms. The orchestration should be dynamic, allowing the system to adapt to varying operational conditions and optimise performance. This includes the ability to shift processing loads based on real-time network conditions, application requirements, and system metrics.

The purpose of raising this requirement is to ensure that the newly added system architecture and functions for semantic processing capability do not negatively impact the operation of legacy systems. Instead, they should enhance overall system functionality and performance in general. Integrating new semantic and legacy 5G systems effectively minimises potential downtime and ensures a smooth transition to more advanced capabilities. Additionally, this approach maximises resource utilization, leveraging the strengths of both traditional and SemCom methods.

4.6 Use-case requirement

The use-case requirements encompass the specific needs and demands associated with each individual use-case. In general, SemCom can function better in applications with large amounts of data exchange.

A more detailed list of these use-cases is elaborated in Section 3 of this deliverable. Additionally, the corresponding KPIs and metrics requirements are provided in [D2.2].

4.7 Performance requirements

4.7.1 Performance requirements per use-case

Performance requirements specify the target performance of the 6G-GOALS architecture for various applications and use-cases. To better examine these requirements, we consider them from two distinct perspectives: 1) classical metrics/KPIs typically defined in communication systems, such as capacity, data rate, latency, reliability, and others; and 2) newly defined semantic metrics/KPIs, which focus on semantic aspects, such as the age of information, relevance of data, and contextual accuracy.

Classical metrics are essential for evaluating the fundamental performance characteristics of the communication system, ensuring it meets the baseline needs for speed, efficiency, and reliability. These metrics help in assessing how well the system can handle large volumes of data, maintain low latency for real-time applications, and ensure high reliability for critical communication.

On the other hand, semantic metrics are crucial for the relevant applications that rely on the meaningful interpretation and timely delivery of data. These metrics evaluate how effectively the system can provide contextually relevant information, manage the freshness of data (age of information), and ensure the accuracy of data interpretation in various use-cases.

For each use-case, a detailed comparison of these two types of metrics/KPIs is provided in [Section 4, D2.2]. This comparison helps in understanding the trade-offs and synergies between traditional performance parameters and the new semantic requirements, providing a comprehensive view of the system's capabilities and areas for improvement. By addressing both classical and semantic performance requirements, the 6G-GOALS architecture aims to deliver a robust, efficient, and intelligent communication system capable of supporting a wide range of future applications.

4.7.2 Energy efficiency

In the following, we focus on the requirements related to energy efficiency due to the main consideration on the network design. Energy efficiency is a major KPI for the semantic and goal-oriented communication paradigm, measuring the communication performance obtained by the system relative to the energy consumed by it. The proper comparison between the energy efficiency delivered by legacy communication modes and the semantic and goal-oriented ones depends on the careful definition of the performance and energy KPIs. Nevertheless, higher energy efficiency is a paramount requirement for the next-generation communication systems that can be addressed by semantic and goal-oriented communications.

- To guarantee that benefits on energy efficiency are obtained, *it is necessary to deploy optimization and compensation strategies for reducing the overall system's energy consumption*, accounting for the energy expenditure introduced by the new components of the semantic and goal-oriented communication systems. In sum, the gains in communication performance combined with the decrease in energy consumption should be higher than the extra consumption introduced by new components.
- Optimizing channel coding with semantic coding/decoding schemes.
- Optimizing radio resources management based on the characteristics of the new communication protocols.

- Reducing energy consumption at UE level using lower processing rate technologies.

The decrease of energy consumption obtained from each previously listed point must be evaluated at the same performance metric level with the aim of delivering a target energy efficiency of the system.

Additional requirements of indirect energy consumption reduction considering semantic and goal-oriented communication usage:

- The refinement of QoS requirements at the different layers of the system taking into account semantic and goal-oriented communications having an indirect impact on both performance and energy consumption by tailoring QoS management to the new communication type.
- The refinement of network slice properties to consider semantic and goal-oriented communication when slice descriptors are taken into account at different radio protocol sub-layers.
- Optionally, when semantic encoding/decoding is not performed at RAN level, the reduction of payload on the transport layer and Core Network user plane by transmitting also semantic information instead of legacy Protocol Data Unit (PDU) payload.

Actions to deploy new semantic and goal-oriented components and modules without increasing the power consumption include:

- The addition of new components such as knowledge databases should be followed by data model optimization and smart knowledge data storage management to limit the impacts on energy due to the additional footprint introduced by them.
- When possible, new semantic modules, as non-real-time ML/AI algorithms, should run on existing frameworks, such as the RIC for O-RAN, reusing available functionalities to leverage the current setup and limit additional footprint on OAM.
- Optimised application programming interfaces (APIs) for data exchange between semantic and goal-oriented entities (semantic plane) are required to limit the traffic between interfaces.
- The replacement of existing real-time encoders/decoders by semantic- and goal-oriented-based ones, at all levels of the data processing path, should include an efficient semantic module location strategy to optimise energy consumption. This strategy could be applied to the whole network, including the UEs, at the deployment and operation phases using an orchestration framework that bases its decisions on analytics provided by the RIC, OAM, and Core Network.

To guarantee a benefit on overall energy efficiency when exploiting semantic and goal-oriented communications, the energy consumption of each related component should be monitored using means developed as native features in the proposed solution, having the following requirements:

- The measurement or estimate of energy consumption at each AI and network entity level requires fine-grained collection and estimate. The collected metrics could be partially derived from the 3GPP defined EE KPIs for 5G RAN and Core. In the case of RAN entities deployed on a cloud-native environment as CaaS or PaaS, existing software components can provide such metrics at this granularity level to be used as main measures for energy KPIs monitoring purposes. In the case of network function virtualisation (NFV) or deployment on “physical server”, energy consumption could be considered at Virtual Machine level or from server power consumption capability provided by

the server manufacturer or defined by the ETSI. This metrics collection can benefit also of existing OAM performance management capabilities such as RAN element management system (EMS) or equivalent.

- The ability to estimate energy consumption at the radio frequency (RF) level. In the case the adopted observability framework is incapable of providing information on the energy KPIs at the RF level, these metrics can be estimated from simulations, taking as inputs the configuration parameters of the radio layers and the UE profiles.
- The comparison with legacy systems. Mapping between the energy KPIs for legacy communications systems and the KPIs for the semantic and goal-oriented ones should be established to obtain consistent and fair energy efficiency comparisons. To this end, selecting KPIs at the application level instead of the network level has the potential to give comparable energy efficiency metrics. Therefore, for a specific use-case, it would be possible to verify if the semantic and goal-oriented communication system is delivering higher energy efficiency than the legacy one.
- Each semantic and goal-oriented algorithm and model must account for the energy consumption in their optimization, which could be included as an optimization goal or a constraint, avoiding energy overspending that might result in a negative energy balance for the overall system.
- The capability to integrate collected or estimated energy consumption KPIs as feedback for being used by prediction model and/or decision-making. The purpose is to include the energy efficiency objective at each stage of the semantic and goals-oriented processing task. The proper trade-off of those energy-saving task execution from UE, BS to RAN, OAM or cross-network domain must be considered. This trade-off conditions the expected impact coverage (locally on specific components versus on the overall system with an end-to-end approach).
- The capability to optimise the different parameters managing the semantic and goal-oriented communication (enabling, for example, closed loops), especially those that impact energy consumption. Those parameters can be defined at RAN level but also at the overall system including the relevant subscription data located in the Core Network subsystem as QoS specified in subscribers 'data or equivalent requirements defined at slice level. Depending on their complexity, these energy reduction control tasks can be achieved using numeric optimization or based on ML techniques.

5 Conclusions

This initial deliverable of the 6G-GOALS project provides a foundation for developing the next-generation semantic and goal-oriented communication paradigm. By presenting a clear vision, conducting a detailed use-case analysis, and providing a taxonomy of system design requirements, we have established some of the key building blocks for research and technology trials in other WPs. The thirteen use-cases, categorised into multimedia-centric, task-oriented, network management, and IoT, demonstrate the transformative potential of the SemCom for 6G. Each use-case is accompanied by system requirements, benefits of semantic communication, and relevant KPIs/metrics. Meanwhile, the system requirement taxonomy addresses key aspects of system design, including architecture, functionality, management and orchestration, integration and compatibility, use-case, and performance, with a focus on RAN and core network design aspects for achieving semantic-awareness. This deliverable will serve as a guide for subsequent technical activities, laying the foundation of application and system design, ensuring that the 6G-GOALS project progresses effectively toward achieving its objectives.

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